

Freedom for the Few – Liberalism in the Network Society

by Britta Noelte

– D R A F T, v3 –

Gaming Liberal Societies

Liberalism promises individual freedom, yet one can observe liberal societies to distribute freedom increasingly unequally. While liberal societies excluding specific groups from freedom follows historical precedence, such as that of Switzerland not allowing women to vote in federal elections prior to 1971 (BK), in these cases, liberalism is usually defended by granting it some time until it has overcome its initial obstacles. In recent years, however, liberal societies have struggled to protect equal individual freedom to an extent that renders the pending full implementation of liberalism an increasingly less plausible excuse. For example, liberal societies are not exempt (Friedlingstein et al., 2022) from failing to mitigate the climate emergency (Pörtner et al., 2022), which causes huge proportions of the world’s population to pay with their current, and future, freedoms, as, e.g. the German Constitutional Court argued (Pittel, 2021), whilst those causing the emergency, namely the fossil fuel industry, make average annual profits of 1.03 trillion US\$ (Verbruggen, 2022). Further examples include the comprehensive surveillance of citizens by liberal governments (Snowden, 2019). For their own benefit, liberal governments effectively dismantle the individual freedom of citizens to decide which information to share and which to keep private. In addition, wealth, with all the freedoms it provides to infringe upon the outcome of a war or the shape of information landscapes, becomes concentrated in the hands of ever fewer people (Zucman, 2019).

By stark contrast, liberalism promises to protect equal individual freedom. To achieve this, equal freedom, assumed to characterize an initial situation – an “estate all men are naturally in, and that is, a state of perfect freedom” (Locke, 1981, ch.2) –, should be protected by requiring any deviation from it to be justified. This claim can be traced throughout the history of liberalism: Mill (1963, vol. 21, p.262) argues that “the burthen of proof is supposed to be with those who are against liberty; [...] The *à priori* presumption is in favour of freedom and impartiality.” Contemporary accounts agree, among them Feinberg (1984, p.9), who says: “Liberty should be the norm; coercion always needs some special justification.” In practice, the liberal order thus establishes two stages, whose chronology my subsequent argument will follow: In *Stage1*, interference by the state is prohibited a priori, in *Stage2*, it is allowed, if publicly justified.

To permit interference with individual freedom, what should count as justification? Contract theory justifies interference with negative freedom of citizens by reference to their agreement, which in the contractarian tradition is based on their prudential self-interests, in contrast to reason or moral considerations of, possibly highly idealized, individuals on which the contractualist tradition is based. Specifically, contractarian thought assumes that everyone is prudentially interested in leaving behind a Hobbesian initial situation of war of everyone against everyone or in mutually beneficial cooperation. From this view, liberalism can be assumed to protect individual freedom by granting priority to an initial situation of equal freedom, from which any deviation needs to further individual prudential interests.

Assuming interference with individual freedom only to be permitted when individuals agree on it based on their prudential self-interests, might not reflect actual individual motivations throughout all cases. Individuals might want to act altruistically and might want to push for and allow jointly created binding rules based on moral considerations. Yet, without doubt, the contractarian assumption is adequate at least for some individuals to some

extent, and my aim here is to examine what might result from this version of the liberal order *insofar* as it holds true.

Indeed, should one expect the liberal order relying on prudential self-interests to protect equal individual freedom? Contractarianism is already known (e.g. by Nussbaum, 2007, p.183-204) to exclude – by design nonetheless – those unable to contribute to mutually beneficial cooperations such as the disabled or the elderly. If someone has little to contribute to a cooperative venture of joint welfare, prudentially interested individuals evidently cannot be assumed to strive to include them, and their preferences, in the contract. One can dispute then, how liberalism, in this version, can be thought of as protecting equal individual freedom whilst systematically excluding specific groups, yet responsibility is usually evaded by reference to exclusion being not a human decision but a consequence of naturally occurring bad luck due to which some lack the ability to contribute value.

Undercutting what one can expect from this version of liberalism, in the following, I will argue for a fault in the basic premise of the liberal order that exceeds exclusion of those unable to contribute value and that should not be attributed to naturally occurring bad luck. This fault becomes visible when adding into consideration the basic social structure the liberal order is implemented in, the network society. I will assume the network society to consist of ubiquitous cooperation between differentiated individuals (for the network society and similar constructs, see e.g., Barney, 2004; Castells, 2004; Stehr, 2017; Webster, 2014), which offers individuals different opportunities to act as associations and thereby to interfere with each other. As liberalism grants priority to a situation of individual negative freedom, individuals can translate the advantage they have thus gained into opportunities for interference with the political process.

To forestall a misunderstanding able to emerge from critiquing the liberal priority of negative freedom, I should state that the situation, obviously, cannot be remedied by making it worse, as authoritarian regimes do. Switching

to 'priority of state interference' to avoid unintended consequences of 'priority of no state interference', cannot assuage the problem, as I will argue, not even by securing this arrangement with democratic institutions for decision making. This is in line with what we can observe: although neoliberalism, at least, is often viewed by its critics along the lines of an "ideology that subordinates all values to an economic rationality" (Whyte, 2019, p.19), conceptualizations that suggest a strong state as a counter, historically, did not recommend themselves by guaranteeing individual freedom. On that account, I want to explore an explanation of the failures of liberal societies that is instead suitable across the dimension of varying state involvement.

Non-Interference

What happens in the initial situation of *Stage1*, then? As jointly agreed-upon political rules cannot be established yet, individuals can mutually interfere with each other, which can result in a "Warre Of Every One Against Every One" (Hobbes, 2012, ch.13) but which, at the same time, gives rise to everyone's interest in being protected by a jointly created political authority. Crucially, this initial situation is regularly assumed to be a neutral, symmetrical starting point, in which individuals are equal from a political standpoint, as "even the weakest has strength enough to kill the strongest" (Hobbes, 2012, ch.13), with approximately equal physical and mental capabilities, and in absence of an environment that influenced the situation to the contrary (see Kraus, 1993; Hampton, 1986, p.25). Everyone can be interfered with by everyone else, but at least hierarchy of any kind is absent, it is claimed. Individuals are assumed to be equally free, which is what should be protected.

However, when examining liberalism as implemented in the network society, I want to contest the premise of actual equal initial freedom. The network society, as outlined above, can be characterized by ubiquitous coop-

eration between differentiated individuals, which, as well as other entities, I will see as nodes in a network. Individuals each with specific properties due to their differentiation can, depending on the overall configuration of their properties as well as that of all other entities, pursue specific actions, which I will view as edges in the network, and which, in turn, may affect the properties of the individuals themselves or those of other entities. How individuals are affected by specific actions will have a certain utility, value or preference satisfaction for them and they should be expected to choose the action that provides the greatest one and to which they would thus agree most.

Insofar as individuals in the network society differentiate, they can produce surplus. As each individual narrows in on specific processes, such as by resuming a specific spot at an assembly line or by acquiring medical knowledge, they can produce multiple units at once, en bloc, and thus save on overhead costs. Subsequently exchanging what they have produced for what they either need personally or as input for their production process, allows them to increase their benefits compared to a situation in which they each acted individually. I will understand surplus as that part of the value created jointly that exceeds aggregated individual production costs. Differentiation is thus beneficial, but, in turn, requires individuals to commit to the development of specific properties, possibly to a significant extent and for a long period of time, and thus locks them in considerably.

Created by way of exchange between differentiated individuals, how will surplus be distributed? Upon having differentiated, individuals exchange resources that are not easily comparable anymore, which prohibits them from switching places conveniently. Distribution of surplus is therefore up for bargaining, which, according to bargaining theory, will be influenced by the availability of alternatives (see Muthoo, 1999) the network offers to an exchange. An individual with better alternatives can use them as bargaining power (Willer, 1999), as a “threat advantage” as Rawls (2001, p.16) calls it, to bias the distribution of surplus in their favor.

A toy example, similar to Muthoo's, illustrates this mechanism. If A values the house he wants to sell at least at 500.000 and B values A 's house she wants to buy at most at 700.000, their joint surplus, originating from their cooperation, would be 200.000. A and B would agree on a selling price of 600.000, thereby halving surplus. Yet, if a third buyer C credibly offered A 649.000, A could use the alternative offer to sell his house to B for 650.000, thus increasing his surplus.

Distributing surplus according to alternatives available, such as when beach-front property is sold lucratively, is usually considered to be in our best interests. Not only is it said to maximise subjective value, as it selects the buyer, who offers the best alternative and for whom the good is thereby considered to be most valuable, if possible for a certain resource, it also works as an incentive to increase production, thus leveling out distribution of surplus on its own.

The network society, however, consisting of ubiquitous cooperation between differentiated individuals, gives rise to a biased distribution of surplus that *deviates* from how subjectively valuable resources are and to which individuals would agree, I claim. Specifically, as individuals differ with regard to the concentration of properties they are connected with, they each have different opportunities to enter and to act as an association and thereby to appropriate surplus without being required to produce value. I will make this point across three cases.

First, individuals differ with regard to their connection to common goods. Common goods such as streetlights or an atmosphere conducive to human life are characterized by a concentration of their benefits so small that restricting access to them would be prohibitively costly. Individuals might very well value a common good, yet as it will provide only a common benefit, but not an individual one whose access could be restricted, and as, for now, it is impossible to obligate everyone to contribute their fair share such that everyone could gain an average benefit, it is de facto not available despite its

potentially significant value.

Crucially, whilst common goods cannot be produced yet despite being valuable, other associations, such as those extracting fossil fuels, can already unite behind resources concentrated enough to allow control of access to them. Then, as alternatives available might deviate from what is valuable to individuals, bargaining over surplus might as well. For example, a fossil fuel company bargaining with customers about the price of gas can gain different amounts of surplus, with and without the alternative of a stable climate being present. If individuals could jointly choose a stable climate as alternative to driving a car, which provided a value of 10, fossil fuel companies would need to decrease the price of gas such that the alternative of driving a car would be more valuable than 10 for customers. This would dent the share of surplus fossil fuel companies could gain from these exchanges. Yet, without the alternative available to customers to jointly pursue a stable climate, fossil fuel companies only have to compete with the much less valuable alternative individuals have of not driving a car but also not being able to access benefits from a more stable climate as these are distributed among all individuals. This allows fossil fuel companies to increase price of gas and thus their share of surplus accordingly. Fossil fuel companies thus bargain with customers in a situation whose alternatives do not adequately reflect what is subjectively valuable, but which is biased by different opportunities to associate and thus to interfere unjustifiably with the distribution of surplus.

Secondly, when individuals enter exchanges with each other, they may differ regarding the concentration of resource they are connected with and thus regarding the opportunity to act as a unified association. If demand for a resource exceeds supply, a supplying party connected with a more concentrated resource can benefit from a bidding war between the demanding parties. As the demanding parties' respective alternative to the exchange, that became significant should the supplying party defect, is worse than the reverse is for the supplying party, the supplying party can effectively play

members of the demanding party off against each other. In this way, the supplying party can depress what the demanding parties can gain. If the demanding parties could associate, for example by unionizing, their share of surplus would increase, yet to do so, they needed a binding agreement for all, which at this stage is not available yet. Distribution of surplus, in this case as well, might only partially reflect how valuable a resource is, but might be biased by how well it allows the exchanging parties, respectively, to act as a unified association.

This might echo a situation described by Adam Smith (1993, Book I, ch.VIII), in which “the masters, being fewer in number, can combine much more easily”. Moreover, the outcome of an exchange between an individual connected to a resource whose units can be merged more easily, such as capital, and other individuals connected to a resource not offering the same opportunities to enter and to act as an association, such as labor, might converge with that of Marx’ analysis of “forced appropriation of surplus value” (Marx, 1902, p.40) produced by workers.

Thirdly, individuals may differ regarding the number of other individuals they share properties with, which might result in groups encompassing some individuals whose concentration in that group is so small that they are considered a minority. In these cases, we should expect distribution of surplus to be biased due to characteristics at the group-level, too. Consider, in comparison, two individuals joining forces to create a common resource. If they differed in which properties they preferred their joint resource to have, they could be both expected to accommodate the other party’s preferences to the same extent, thus halving surplus at the bottom line. However, cooperation between a group of individuals consisting of a majority wanting one version and a minority wanting another, insofar as the alternative to that cooperation, should this one fail, is better for the majority due to economies of scale, requires the minority to adapt to the preferences of the majority, which reduces their share of surplus by the need to subtract accommodation

costs.

Crucially, it is the influence of the concentration of individuals in a group, a *group-level*-characteristic, which might, depending on actual parameters, lead to a tyranny of the majority. Although this danger is known by liberal thought, it is often assumed to be dealt with by the establishment of individual rights guaranteeing a minimum of quality of life and social participation. Yet, this does not necessarily need to reflect subjective value produced, and even if individual rights are established at the same time as freedom from state interference is given priority, their effect depends on their actual implementation and the weight they are in fact given in conflicting cases. Insofar as the effectiveness of individual rights can be perforated, members of the majority can systematically interfere unjustifiably with those of the minority.

In all three cases, priority to individual freedom from interference by the state is granted, but the situation is only cleared *partially* of interference by powerful groups: while the state is being kept in check, this, at the same time, leaves individuals vulnerable to interference with distribution of surplus by other powerful groups already able to associate and ready to benefit at their expense without providing value.

Choosing the liberal principle of 'priority of negative freedom' thus comes with the danger of choosing to stratify a society according to their members' opportunities to associate, without necessarily being connected to production of value. In the network society, one should expect this pattern to be present consistently due to the stability of individual differentiations, in contrast to a rather noisy setup whose effects canceled each other out, in the long run. For this reason, I claim individuals should not be considered to be politically equal, initially, but rather that some, which I will henceforth call *Srpls.apprs*, are able to interfere unjustifiably with distribution of surplus. By wanting to protect individuals from the state as a powerful association, *Stage1* in fact leaves individuals vulnerable to the unjustified interference of *Srpls.apprs*.

Finally, *Srpls.apprs* can choose whether to continue pursuing certain, or

whether to reinvest their surplus in certain further, exchanges, thereby interfering with the natural or social conditions of future exchanges in ways that increase their future opportunity to interfere with distribution of surplus. For example, when fossil fuel companies choose to continue drilling or when they choose to reinvest surplus they have appropriated into expanding oilfields, they ultimately exacerbate the occurrence of heat waves. As their exchanging parties, on account of this, increasingly need to regulate surrounding air temperature, for which they might rely on fossil fuels, *Srpls.apprs* can gain even more surplus. In this way, they can start a positive feedback loop, which I will call *Loop1* and with the help of which they could expand even a slight initial advantage into a huge one, one iteration followed by the next.

Interference

Yet, even if we assumed liberalism indeed to start off from a biased initial situation, in which individuals are politically unequal, it could be argued that resulting unjustified interference could simply be corrected in *Stage2*. By implementing political rules that establish what individuals actually decide or would agree to and which, in turn, affect a class of exchanges, distribution of surplus can be corrected as wanted. As everyone is given the same political weight when creating these rules, they should be presumed able to rectify any prior bias. Even if some party tried to use political instruments to bias a rule in their favor to keep prior interference in place, the political process could cancel out these efforts. Diverging interests are assumed to meet half-way, when everyone is given the same opportunities for political influence.

However, distribution of surplus cannot be corrected in *Stage2* as wanted, I will argue. Since liberalism gives priority to *Stage1* over *Stage2*, individuals enter *Stage2* not as equally free to define the political process, but associated with different levels of concentration of properties and thereby different opportunities to act in association, which allows some of them to interfere

with the political process unjustifiably. They can do so in two ways.

First, some individuals enter *Stage2* with better opportunities to act as an association in the political arena, as they could already pool more of a more concentrated resource in *Stage1*, when they were better able to gain surplus. Establishing a rule is a time-consuming endeavor. A problem needs to be identified, its embedding in a potentially complex situation needs to be understood, awareness and public attention need to be raised, suitable solutions need to be found, compared and debated and political instruments need to be found and adapted. While the political machinery is running, *Srpls.apprs* could have already gained surplus, which equips them with an advantage in money, social status or time that subsequently provides them with better alternatives to influence the political process, either via lobbying or via manipulating public perception of the respective issue. For example, those with advantages in resources can better pay for lobbying efforts that contribute to block ambitious climate policies (see Vesa et al., 2020) or for efforts that shape public opinion about climate change (see Dür, 2019). Ultimately, their efforts might interfere with rules dealing with the according issues, in their favor, at the expense of what other individuals would agree to or want.

Secondly, although individuals with competing interests could advocate for their position too, in comparison, as a cluster of atomistic entities, they had to contend with difficulties of pooling their resources. Some individuals enter *Stage2* with better opportunities to act as an association in the political arena as they were already better able to unite behind shared interests in *Stage1* as well as to assemble the necessary social and natural conditions for their preferred solution, whilst others still need to find resources – of which they have even less, at that – to sponsor the process of finding common ground and to arrive at an agreement. As *Srpls.apprs* are already prepared to act, whilst others still need to find and promote a compromise between a much larger set of much more contentious issues with much bigger potential

for change, they are better able to interfere with the political process in order to further their own interests, at the expense of what would be wanted by others.

Complementary to some individuals having better opportunities than others to further their own interests when horizontally competing for political influence, in a vertical exchange between politicians and their citizens, the prior are better able to further their own interests due to a more favorable concentration of properties of their resource. In an exchange between citizens and a politician that grants the politician a salary and a certain social role entailing opportunities for political influence and that, in return, allows citizens to delegate decision making to the politician such that they do not need to track every policy matter in detail, the politician acts as a unified, as a concentrated actor with better alternatives available. For example, he can accept lobbying money or campaign financing for a minor adaptation of a rule he is favoring, which to stop required a multitude of possibly quite diverse individuals to know, understand and care about it as well as to find a joint decision about the affected specific, often complicated, policy matter, whilst each individual is incentivized to freeride. Thus, to a certain extent, the politician can interfere unjustifiably with the output of the political process, against what citizens would value or want.

Therefore, as individuals enter *Stage2* with different levels of concentration of certain properties, some can use these to better act as an overpowering association, which enables them to interfere unjustifiably with the political process and its output in their favor, at the expense of what is valued or wanted. They can either impede any necessary correction whose need results from unjustified interference in *Stage1* or they can bias political output even further in favor of their own interests. As the resulting political rules affect specific sets of exchanges, *Srpls.apprs* can keep appropriating, or appropriate even more, surplus, thus starting another positive feedback loop, *Loop2*, which secures their benefits or even increases them, over a prolonged

time. While in *Stage1*, *Srpls.apprs* could start a positive feedback loop by choosing solutions that, horizontally, interfere with the other party's future natural or social alternatives, in *Stage2*, they can reinvest surplus such that they can interfere with the other party's future alternatives vertically, via the political process. Although the liberal order wants to protect citizens from unjustified interference by the state, it not only leaves them vulnerable to unjustified interference by other powerful actors, but insofar as this protection is systemically prone to being perforated, it is unable to do so in the first place.

Freedom for the Few

Liberalism aims to protect equal individual freedom, yet when implemented in the network society consisting of ubiquitous cooperation between differentiated individuals, I argued, it can be expected to produce the reverse, increasingly unequal freedom. By viewing individuals as atomistic parts of an unconsolidated cluster who are initially politically equal, when, in fact, in the network society they differ regarding opportunities to enter and act as associations, liberalism ultimately enables some to interfere unjustifiably with others, in deviation of what the latter would value or want. As liberalism grants priority to this situation, it equips some individuals to enter the political process as an association, effectively enabling them to interfere unjustifiably with the political rules it produces. Conversely, as some individuals are provided with opportunities for interference, the negative freedom of those that are interfered with decreases.

As *Srpls.apprs* can use their opportunities to interfere with distribution of surplus to interfere, subsequently, with natural, social and political conditions and thus to interfere with distribution of surplus even further, effectively starting positive feedback loops in their favor, resulting interference might be quite large, even if initial inequality has been minimal, as is characteristic for

dynamic systems. Insofar as liberalism is relying on contractarian prudential self-interests of individuals as justification for interference, it should be expected not only to exclude those from the contract unable to contribute value due to natural bad luck, but to stratify society systematically, and to corroborate this stratification, according to individual differences in opportunity to associate, without necessarily being connected to value produced.

Admittedly, this analysis is based on only coarse-grained basic characteristics of the liberal order and the network society each, which, in reality, are embedded in ecosystems of further institutions that include checks and balances, minority rights, labor unions, a multitude of rules against e.g. political malpractice etc. and which altogether should protect against initial inequality of freedom. Yet, these safeguards can be, and indeed are, eroded in the political process by way of the mechanisms described above, possibly proving powerless against the move of liberal societies along a trajectory that eventually leads them to abolish their foundation of individual freedom altogether.

It is the danger of this segue, that might justify criticizing priority of negative freedom, as, when implemented in the network society, the liberal order might indeed produce increasing levels of concentration that authoritarian forces might gain, make use of or collude with, and that might allow them to increasingly interfere with citizens, continually extending their initial advantage over those dissenting. Actual inequalities in the distribution of freedom that liberal societies debate under the header of identity politics, might not be a price to pay for the continued support of a presumably self-interested majority, but hint at a predestined breaking point for a system with potential to turn against these very interests, too.

What about regimes that evaded the described pitfalls of 'priority of negative freedom' by establishing democratic institutions to protect a setup, in which every individual action was, by default, either prohibited or needed to be in pursuit of a common goal? Prohibiting fossil fuel emissions unless

jointly allowed by democratic process, for example, appears beneficial in a society struggling heavily to decrease them. Yet, such a regime still offered an initial advantage to some in opportunities to interfere with others. In case individual action is restricted by default, members of the state's regulating agencies in charge of facilitating democratic decisions about when to lift restrictions, would be granted a huge area of discretion, which they might use to produce political rules for their own benefit, whilst the public was unable to keep up this much oversight. Therefore, if state actors per se might utilize an initial advantage just as well as non-state actors, when given the opportunity, we should pivot from a debate about varying state involvement to one directly asking how individuals can benefit from associations without being overpowered by their vested interests.

This question is becoming increasingly urgent, as associations become ever more powerful due to social and technological progress (compare, e.g., with Bak-Coleman et al., 2021). Newly gained social and technological abilities allow the creation of ever denser and vaster network structures, but also facilitate an expanse of the part of the network under human control. Whereas, for example, at the time of writing of Feinberg (1973, p.12) a storm did not count as interference by a powerful external social actor, nowadays, it increasingly should (see Pörtner et al., 2022). As networks and their components become bigger, so do the opportunities to gain benefits unjustifiably, if an association is able to capture the surplus they produce.

References

- Joseph B Bak-Coleman, Mark Alfano, Wolfram Barfuss, Carl T Bergstrom, Miguel A Centeno, Iain D Couzin, Jonathan F Donges, Mirta Galesic, Andrew S Gersick, Jennifer Jacquet, et al. Stewardship of global collective behavior. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 118(27): e2025764118, 2021.
- Darin David Barney. *The Network Society*, volume 2. Polity, 2004.
- Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft Bundeskanzlei BK. Volksabstimmung vom 07.02.1971. <https://www.bk.admin.ch/ch/d/pore/va/19710207/index.html>.
- Manuel Castells. *The Network Society: A Cross-cultural Perspective*. Edward Elgar Publishing, Incorporated, 2004.
- Andreas Dür. How interest groups influence public opinion: Arguments matter more than the sources. *European Journal of Political Research*, 58(2): 514–535, 2019.
- Joel Feinberg. *Social Philosophy*. Prentice-Hall, Englewood Cliffs, N.J., 1973.
- Joel Feinberg. *Harm to Others*. Oxford University Press, USA, 1984.
- Pierre Friedlingstein, Michael O’sullivan, Matthew W Jones, Robbie M Andrew, Luke Gregor, Judith Hauck, Corinne Le Quéré, Ingrid T Lujckx, Are Olsen, Glen P Peters, et al. Global carbon budget 2022. *Earth System Science Data Discussions*, 2022:1–159, 2022.
- Jean Hampton. *Hobbes and the Social Contract Tradition*. Cambridge University Press, 1986.

- Thomas Hobbes. *Leviathan / Thomas Hobbes ; edited by J.C.A. Gaskin, introduced by Alan Ryan, illustrated by Mike Wilks.* The Folio Society, 2012.
- Jody S Kraus. *The Limits of Hobbesian Contractarianism.* Cambridge University Press Cambridge, 1993.
- John Locke. *An Essay Concerning the True Original, Extent and End of Civil Government,* volume 35. Pergamon Press, 1981.
- Karl Marx. *Wage-labor and Capital.* New York Labor News Company, 1902.
- Abhinay Muthoo. *Bargaining Theory with Applications.* Cambridge University Press, 1999.
- Martha C Nussbaum. *Frontiers of Justice: Disability, Nationality, Species Membership.* Harvard University Press, 2007.
- Karen Pittel. Der Beschluss des Bundesverfassungsgerichts und die intertemporale Verteilung der Lasten von Klimapolitik. *Ifo Schnelldienst*, 74(6): 29–33, 2021.
- Hans-Otto Pörtner, Debra C Roberts, Melinda Tignor, Elvira Poloczanska, Katja Mintenbeck, Andrés Alegría, Marlies Craig, Stefanie Langsdorf, Sina Löschke, Vincent Möller, et al. IPCC 2022: Climate Change 2022: impacts, adaptation and vulnerability: working group II contribution to the sixth assessment report of the intergovernmental panel on climate change. 2022.
- John Rawls. *Justice as Fairness: A Restatement.* Harvard University Press, 2001.
- Adam Smith. *An inquiry into the nature and causes of the wealth of nations : a selected edition / Adam Smith. Ed. with an introd. and commentary by Kathryn Sutherland.* Oxford University Press, 1993.

- Edward Snowden. *Permanent Record: A Memoir of a Reluctant Whistleblower*. Pan Macmillan, 2019.
- Nico Stehr. Knowledge societies. In *Society and Knowledge*, pages 299–322. Routledge, 2017.
- Mill John Stuart and J Robson. The collected works of John Stuart Mill. Ed. John M. Robson and Jack Stillinger. Toronto: U of Toronto P, 1963.
- Aviel Verbruggen. The geopolitics of trillion us\$ oil & gas rents. *International Journal of Sustainable Energy Planning and Management*, 36:3–10, 2022.
- Juho Vesa, Antti Gronow, and Tuomas Ylä-Anttila. The quiet opposition: How the pro-economy lobby influences climate policy. *Global Environmental Change*, 63:102117, 2020.
- Frank Webster. *Theories of the Information Society*. Routledge, 2014.
- Jessica Whyte. *The Morals of the Market: Human Rights and the Rise of Neoliberalism*. Verso Books, 2019.
- David Willer. *Network Exchange Theory*. Bloomsbury Publishing USA, 1999.
- Gabriel Zucman. Global wealth inequality. *Annual Review of Economics*, 11: 109–138, 2019.

© 2025. This work is licensed under a CC BY-SA 4.0 license.